

Integrated Data Analytics and Regression Techniques for Real-time Anomaly Detection in Industrial Processes

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Introduction

Process monitoring in refinery operations is often affected by discrepancies between high-frequency online analyzer data and infrequent laboratory measurements. This study, conducted in collaboration with Slovnaft, a.s., presents a multi-fidelity modeling framework that combines both static and dynamic soft-sensor designs to improve online measurement reliability. We apply data-driven feature selection methods (including Principal Component Regression, Partial Least Squares, LASSO, and Stepwise Regression) to identify the most relevant input variables. To address the temporal dependencies present with recycle streams, we incorporate time-lagged features within a dynamic model identified using the SIPPY system identification toolbox. A Gaussian Process model, built using composite kernels, is then trained to predict the deviations between low-fidelity analyzer measurements and high-fidelity laboratory values. The resulting multi-fidelity soft sensor corrects the measured data to predict the true value, improving prediction accuracy and supporting more informed real-time decision-making.

Problem Definition

Error between the sensor and laboratory samples.

Simplified flow chart describing the integrated alkylation unit.

Methodology & Results

RMSE comparison of lab samples against applied approaches.

Comparison	Training	Testing
Lab (y_{HF}) – Analyzer (y_{LF})	0.63	0.80
Lab (y_{HF}) – Model (\hat{y}_{HF})	0.18	0.91
Lab (y_{HF}) – Model (\hat{y}_{MF} , static)	0.22	0.46
Lab (y_{HF}) – Model (\hat{y}_{MF} , dynamic)	0.31	0.38

Gaussian Process Definition & Implemented Composite Kernel:

$$\hat{\Delta} \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(x), k(x, x'))$$

$$k(x, x') = \underbrace{C \cdot \sigma^2 e^{-\frac{\|x-x'\|^2}{2\ell^2}}}_{\text{Constant} \times \text{RBF}} + \underbrace{e^{-\frac{2 \sin^2(\frac{\pi \|x-x'\|}{p})}{\ell^2}}}_{\text{Periodic}} + \underbrace{\sigma^2 \delta_{x,x'}}_{\text{White Noise}}$$

Multi-Fidelity Correction Implementation:

Gaussian Process Regression

Proposed Multi-Fidelity Prediction Model

Conclusions

The proposed dynamic multi-fidelity model outperforms traditional static and dynamic models by accurately capturing deviations between online analyzer readings and laboratory measurements. It achieves over a 50% improvement in accuracy compared to the currently deployed online analyzer. These results demonstrate the potential to reduce reliance on laboratory sampling, lower operational costs, and strengthen real-time decision-making in industrial operations.

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